

Actinodaphnine. An Alkaloid from *Actinodaphne Hookeri*, Meissn.

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Actinodaphne, vern., *Pisi* (Bomb.) " belongs to a genus of trees or bushes (N. O. *Laurineae*) comprising of about 50 species of which 9 or 10 are Indian, inhabiting the warm, moist forests of the lower hills. It is found common in eastern and western Ghats of S. India and in Kanara and particularly in Mahableshwar. A cold infusion of the leaves is mucilaginous and is used in urinary disorders and in diabetes" (Dymock). Allied to *Actinodaphne* are the *Litsea* species and the best known of which is *Litsea sebifera*, vern., *Maidu lakri* (Hind.). It is a very popular Indian drug and from its bark an alkaloid has been isolated which is identical with laurotetanine, an alkaloid, isolated by N. Greshoff from three species of Java *Litsea*s (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3537). This is also said to be present in several other plants belonging to the N. O. *Laurineae*.

The present work was undertaken to find if laurotetanine was the principal active constituent of *Actinodaphne hookeri*, which is reputed in Ayurvedic system of medicine to be efficacious in diabetic diseases. And for this purpose the bark of the tree was extracted in the usual manner which yielded about 0.7 per cent. of an alkaloid and the pure product from this was obtained on repeated crystallisation from suitable solvents, as it was only in this manner that the last traces of the colouring matter were possible to remove. The alkaloid crystallises in stout prisms, m.p. 210–11°. The analytical data, molecular weight, equivalent weight, etc., all tend to indicate for the alkaloid the formula $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N$ and a molecular weight of 313. It has been found to contain a hydroxyl, a methoxyl and a N-methyl group. Possibilities of a second hydroxyl and methoxyl group have also been explored but with negative results. The alkaloid gives no oxime or a phenylhydrazone and therefore, the absence of an aldehydic or carbonyl grouping is strongly suspected. From these it appears that the alkaloid from *Actinodaphne hookeri* bark is quite different from laurotetanine which contains three

methoxyl and one hydroxyl group. It is, therefore, proposed to designate this alkaloid as *Actinodaphnine*.

There appears to be a certain similarity between actinodaphnine and bebeerine, an alkaloid found in the bark of *Nectandra rodiaei* and *Harandia sonora* (N. O. *Laurineae*). Bebeerine crystallises from methyl alcohol in small prisms, m. p. 214°. It is soluble in alkalis. It has a formula of $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$; it is a tertiary base containing one methoxyl, one hydroxyl and one N-methyl group, but in the physical data of its salts it is quite different to those of actinodaphnine (Scholtz, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1898, 236, 530).

The leaves of *Actinodaphne hookeri* were also examined and a dark brown amorphous base was isolated but the quantity was too small for proper identification. The alkaloid forms amorphous salts and has been found to possess an acid equivalent of 487. The salts of actinodaphnine, on the other hand, are all easily crystallisable and from this it appears that the leaves contain a different alkaloid from that contained in the bark of the tree.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Extraction of the alkaloid from the bark.—Various methods were tried for extraction of the alkaloid with a view to getting the best yield and the one finally adopted is as follows: 500 G. of the finely powdered bark (containing 9 p. c. moisture) was mixed with sodium carbonate (200 g.), triturated with a little water (100 g.) and extracted with 90 p. c. alcohol by cold percolation till the alcohol was colourless. The alcohol from the extract was completely removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the residue extracted several times with 3 p. c. acetic acid. The colouring matter from the extract was removed by precipitation with lead acetate and after removal of the excess of lead acetate and sulphuretted hydrogen in the usual manner, the alkaloid was precipitated with ammonia. If at this stage the acid liquors are still coloured, the same can be removed by treatment with animal charcoal. The precipitated base was extracted with excess of ether which dissolved the base but very little of the colouring matter. The ethereal extract on drying over anhydrous magnesium sulphate was distilled to remove the solvent when the alkaloid was left behind as a white crystalline powder in a yield of about 0.7 p. c. The usual chloroform-ether extraction gave only 0.5 p. c. yield. This

procedure has an additional disadvantage in that the alkaloid could never be completely freed from the colouring matter when chloroform was employed for extraction.

The crude alkaloid, obtained in the above manner, was crystallised from acetone containing a little water and the crystals so formed were dried in air on a porous tile melting at 206–7°. These still retained some colouring matter which was possible to remove only on crystallisation from benzene, and on final crystallisation from absolute alcohol the alkaloid was obtained in prismatic needles, m. p. 210°–11°. (Found: C, 68.8; H, 5.8; N, 4.3; M. W., 310 (Rast). $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N$ requires C, 69.0; H, 6.1; N, 4.5 per cent.; M. W., 313).

Actinodaphnine is *dextrorotatory*, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +32.77^\circ$ in absolute alcohol. It does not contain any water of crystallisation as its weight and melting point remain unaltered on drying at 105° for several hours. It is almost insoluble in water but dissolves freely in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, and benzene and is sparingly soluble in ether. In most of the solvents it shows a pale blue fluorescence. On exposure to light it darkens. It dissolves in caustic alkalis from which it is recovered unchanged but it is insoluble in sodium carbonate. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a beautiful pink colour which on standing deepens to purple and on warming to reddish brown or black. In cold concentrated sulphuric acid containing traces of dichromate or nitric acid it develops a deep blue colour while with nitric acid alone it forms a deep yellowish brown colour. Aqueous solution of its hydrochloride gives a reddish brown coloration with dilute ferric chloride solution.

Actinodaphnine hydrochloride was obtained by dissolving the base in alcohol and adding alcoholic acid. On addition of ether to the above mixture and standing, the hydrochloride crystallised out in needles and these on twice recrystallisation from alcohol and ether gave fine silky needles, m. p. 280–81° with frothing and decomposition. (Found: HCl, 10.15. $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N$, HCl requires HCl, 10.3 per cent.). It is only moderately soluble in cold water and its aqueous solution is *dextrorotatory*, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +8^\circ-45'$. The hydrochloride when prepared and crystallised from aqueous solution and dried in air melts at 280° and no water of crystallisation was found even when kept at 105° for a few hours.

Hydroiodide was prepared by suspending the base in methyl alcohol and adding hydroiodic acid, also dissolved in methyl alcohol,

till just faintly acidic. On addition of ether to form opalescence and on standing stout prismatic needles separated which on recrystallisation from alcohol melted at $264-65^{\circ}$ with frothing and decomposition. (Found: HI, 29.3. $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N$, HI requires HI, 29.0 per cent.).

Sulphate.—The base was suspended in water and dilute sulphuric acid added till just acidic. The sulphate rapidly crystallised out in fine silky needles from the solution in which it is only moderately soluble. Recrystallisation from dilute alcohol gave colourless silky needles which turn yellow or brown on keeping in evacuated desiccator. The sulphate contains 3 molecules of water of crystallisation. The dried salt melts at $249-50^{\circ}$ (decomp.). [Found: H_2SO_4 , 13.7. $(C_{18}H_{19}O_4N)_2 \cdot H_2SO_4$ requires H_2SO_4 , 13.3 per cent.].

Picrate was prepared in the usual manner and on recrystallisation from dilute alcohol separated in fine silky needles, containing one molecule of water of crystallisation. The dried salt decomposes at $220-22^{\circ}$ without melting.

Methiodide was obtained by refluxing on a water-bath a mixture of the base (2 g.) in methyl alcohol (60 c.c.) and methyl iodide (4 g.). On removal of the solvent the methiodide separated as brown silky needles and on recrystallisation from alcohol-ether mixture, melted at $243-44^{\circ}$. (Found: CH_3I , 31.4. $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N$, CH_3I requires CH_3I , 31.2 per cent.).

Methoxyl group was determined by Perkin's modification of Zeisel's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, **83**, 1367). (Found: OCH_3 , 13.9. $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N$ requires OCH_3 , 9.9 per cent.). The results for methoxyl group were intermediate between the values calculated for one and two methoxyl group and is slightly less than that required for one methoxyl and one N-methyl group and from this it appears that the alkaloid contains one OCH_3 and one NCH_3 group which partially decomposes to give the higher values for OCH_3 .

Hydroxyl group.—Actinodaphnine could not be acetylated by direct treatment with acetyl chloride as in the case of laurotetanine (Filepe, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1898, **236**, 601). It was, therefore, acetylated by heating 2 g. of the base dissolved in excess of acetic anhydride on a water-bath at $70^{\circ}-75^{\circ}$. After about 3 hours heating the solution was poured in water when the acetylated product precipitated as a white powder. This was collected, dried and recrystallised from ethyl acetate as light brown tufts of prisms. Dried at 105° it melted at $229-30^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 67.9; H, 5.5. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3N \cdot OAc$)

requires C, 67.6 ; H, 5.9 per cent.). The acetylated product (dry) was hydrolysed with $N/2$ alcoholic potash, on a waterbath for 1 hour. (Found: OAc, 155.7. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3N \cdot OAc$ requires, 157.7).

Benzoylation was conducted in the usual manner by treating the base (2 g.) with benzoyl. chloride (12 c.c.). The product when crystallised from alcohol and ethyl acetate, was obtained as light yellow plates, m.p. 232—33°.

Summary.

1. From the bark of *Actinodaphne hookeri* a new alkaloid has been isolated which is different from the alkaloids, laurotetanine, bebeerine and buxine found in certain plants of the N. O. *Laurineae*. The new alkaloid has been designated as actinodaophnine.

2. The preliminary examination shows it to possess the formula $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N$, Mol. wt. 313 and contain a methoxyl, a N-methyl and a hydroxyl group.

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